

Fruitful Polycarp: Imagery and Symbolism in *The Martyrdom of Polycarp*

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Abstract: Early martyrdom accounts are replete with depictions of the martyrs themselves embodied as fruit, bread, wine, and, more generally, as food. The Martyrdom of St Polycarp is no exception; these themes take a central place in the narrative depiction of the martyr. This paper explores these themes in the broader context of the Old Testament burnt offering, the eucharistic meal, St Paul's imagery of grafting, and the Christian concept of fruitfulness and the vine. In so doing, it endeavours to contextualise the martyrdom of St Polycarp within the broader early Christian tradition of floral and comestible imagery and symbolism. As part of that discussion, it also touches on important Orthodox themes related to those symbols and the act of martyrdom such as suffering, kenosis, and theosis.

Keywords: Polycarp, martyrdom, symbolism, Eucharist, kenosis, theosis, hagiography

The *Martyrdom of Polycarp* is one of several early Christian martyrdom accounts which set the tone for subsequent hagiographical literature of its kind.¹ In doing so, it draws from a number of earlier biblical motifs which directly relate to fruit, wheat, bread, wine, and the vine. As this paper will demonstrate, the presence

1 On the general reception of *The Martyrdom of Polycarp* as well as a careful discussion of textual theories and considerations of authenticity, see *Polycarp's Epistle to the Philippians and the Martyrdom of Polycarp: Introduction, Text, and Commentary*, ed. Paul Hartog (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2013), esp. 28-32; also the older study by William R. Schoedel, *Polycarp, Martyrdom of Polycarp, Fragments of Papias in The Apostolic Fathers, Volume V:* (Eugene: Wipf & Stock, 1967, 2020), and P. N. Harrison, *Polycarp's two epistles to the Philippians* (London: Cambridge University Press, 1936). A segment of the discussion has focused on Polycarp's status as bishop in the early church, a question that is largely unrelated to our thesis here. For the Greek text of the Martyrdom, see Μαρτύριον Πολυκάρπου, in J. P. Migne, *Patrologia Graeca* (hereinafter 'PG'), vol. 5, cols. 1029-1046.

of such floral and comestible themes and elements in the *Martyrdom* is not at all accidental. For the Christian, symbols and images which the account employs not only derive from Holy Scripture but also extend into the Church's liturgical art, praxis and culture to the present. In this context, the martyrdom of Polycarp—and the eponymous work—serve as a paradigm around which early Christian martyrdom came to be both depicted and understood.

By providing a very early Christian framework for these symbols, *The Martyrdom of Polycarp* not only provides a context for the meaning and understanding of subsequent Christian martyrdoms and the Eucharist, it also introduces some of the language according to which the Orthodox Church's later understanding of salvation as *theosis*, the union with God in Christ, is practically achieved. That is to say, in the context of suffering and martyrdom, union with God in Christ is mystically accomplished by participatory and fruitful self-offering, the pouring out of the self as a kenotic offering to God and the world.²

2 Though there has been much development in the modern study and understanding of sacrifice in recent years, it should be noted here that sacrifice as understood in Orthodox Christianity is not merely propitiatory. Rather, sacrifice as the outpouring of the self in love for the world is captured in the concept of *kenosis* (κένωσις). In this sense it is voluntary self-emptying and self-denial springing forth from love. The premier understanding of this has been the condescension of Christ in voluntarily emptying himself of that which was his by divine right, in order to assume our lowly human nature and the accompanying suffering in the flesh. The foundational idea behind this teaching having been expressed in St Paul's letter to the Philippians: "Have this mind among yourselves, which is yours in Christ Jesus, who, though he was in the form of God, did not count equality with God a thing to be grasped, but emptied (ἐκένωσεν) himself, taking the form of a servant, being born in the likeness of men. And being found in human form he humbled himself and became obedient unto death, even death on a cross" (Phil 2:5-8).

Floral and Comestible Symbols in Scripture and the Passion Narratives³

In order to understand the symbolic meaning contained within *The Martyrdom of Polycarp*, it is necessary to keep in mind the previously established symbolism presented in Holy Scripture. Throughout Scripture—as in ancient culture—fruits are symbolic of virtues or good deeds in accordance with the law of God (Isa 5, 27:6; Mt 3:8, 10; Gal 6:8-9). Christ’s warning regarding false prophets as fruitless trees is a vivid example of this meaning: “every sound tree bears good fruit, but the bad tree bears evil fruit. A sound tree cannot bear evil fruit, nor can a bad tree bear good fruit” (Mt 7:17-18).

In the epistles of St Paul, the fruits of Christian virtue are a product of the Spirit and are contrasted with the works of the flesh. They are also, notably, ripened through self-emptying *kenosis* and crucifixion:⁴

Now the works of the flesh are plain: fornication, impurity, licentiousness, idolatry, sorcery, enmity, strife, jealousy, anger, selfishness, dissension, party spirit, envy, drunkenness, carousing, and the like. I warn you, as I warned you before, that those who do such things shall not inherit the kingdom of God. But the fruit of the Spirit [καρπὸς τοῦ πνεύματός] is love, joy, peace, patience, kindness, goodness, faithfulness, gentleness, self-control; against such there is no law. And those who belong to Christ Jesus have crucified the flesh with its passions and desires (Gal 5:19-24).

Owing in part to such descriptions as this, the depiction of the fruits of Christian life by St Paul naturally became tied up with the passion of

3 For more on the background of floral and sacrificial symbols in the Bible, reference my more in-depth studies: Christopher Lockwood, ‘Sacred Tree, Fruit of Immortality: A Brief Introduction to Religious Floral Symbolism’ (with Albanian translation), in *Flora in Arts and Artefacts of the Korça Region: Twelfth Century BC to Twentieth Century AD*, ed. K. Giakoumis (Tirana: Pegi, 2018), 21-39; and chapter five of my forthcoming book: Christopher Lockwood, *Types and Symbols in the Bible* (Alhambra, CA: Sebastian Press, forthcoming).

4 The idea here being linked directly again to *kenosis* as discussed in footnote 2.

Christ. For in being hung upon the tree of the Cross (Gal 3:13), the body and blood of Christ are realised as typological fulfilments of the fruit of eternal life hung upon the tree of life (Gen 2:9, 3:22). In this way the fruit of eternal life, “the medicine of immortality,”⁵ is ripened through the suffering of the passion of Christ, who is Himself hung upon the tree of the Cross. And in a vision of the future kingdom found in the Book of Revelation, it is specifically the leaves of this tree and its twelve kinds of fruit which are offered for the healing of the nations (Rev 22:1-2).⁶

Among the early Fathers of the Church, the Eucharist came to be regarded in this very light as a share in the cup of the suffering Lord (cf. Mt 20:22). To share in the cup of the Lord was therefore inextricably linked to righteous suffering and the participation with Christ and all His saints in the crucifixion of sin by means of suffering in the flesh (Col 3:5; Gal 5:24). This mystery came to be summed up in the eucharistic cup, into which all God’s people offer themselves up to commune with Christ and one another. Moreover, just as the suffering flesh upon the Cross is the fruit of the tree of life, it is also itself the bread of life, offered for the life of the world: “I am the living bread which came down from heaven; if any one eats of this bread, he will live for ever; and the bread which I shall give for the life of the world is my flesh” (Jn 6:51).

5 This line comes from a phrase used by St Ignatius of Antioch, who was acquainted with St Polycarp and whose martyrdom will also be discussed below: “... breaking one bread, which is the medicine of immortality, the antidote that we should not die but live in Jesus Christ forever.” St Ignatius of Antioch, *Ignatius to the Ephesians* (20), in *The Apostolic Fathers: A New Translation*, trans. Rick Brannan (Bellingham: Lexham, 2017), 81-82 (PG 5:661).

6 The reference to twelve kinds of fruit in this passage of Revelation establishes further the communion between the suffering of Christ on the cross and the fruitful suffering of his saints: “... also, on either side of the river, the tree of life with its twelve kinds of fruit, yielding its fruit each month; and the leaves of the tree were for the healing of the nations” (Rev 22:2). The number twelve is a numerical symbol of the collective people of God. There are twelve tribes who descend from the twelve patriarchs of Israel just as there are twelve Apostles. Within the same book there are also notably 144,000 virgins who follow the Lamb (Rev 14:1): that is, twelve times twelve thousand.

Because in the teaching of the Lord Jesus Christ, the act of dying for one's friends is the highest act of love (Jn 15:13), to pour out one's life in love for God and neighbour is understood to be the highest virtuous achievement for a Christian. For doing so mystically unites the offeror to Christ through the laying down of one's life. This sacrifice establishes the martyr as a fruitful member of Christ's body in a way that goes beyond merely being 'fruitful' in terms of external moral behaviour. Martyrdom, therefore, represents the ideal *telos* of Christian virtue and the attainment of perfect union with Christ by means of obedient and self-sacrificial imitation—obedience itself being one of the principal means towards *theosis* as mystical communion with the Lord.⁷

Within the symbolic representations already mentioned, Christ delivered several parables involving wheat and the field (esp. Mt 13; Mk 4), and in another passage from the Gospel of John depicted himself as "the vine" (Jn 15). "I am the vine, you are the branches. He who abides in me, and I in him, he it is that bears much fruit (καρπὸν πολύν),⁸ for apart from me you can do nothing" (Jn 15:5). These floral symbols have great significance and again reflect the mystery of the Kingdom of God. The field is an image of the world planted with the seed of the word by the Lord himself: "He who sows the good seed is the Son of Man; the field is the world, and the good seed means the sons of the kingdom" (Mt 13:37-38).⁹ And yet, the good wheat which has been planted must fall into the

7 Though much later, Saint Nicholas Cabasilas has stated that our entire salvation depends upon two things: "The first is that we be initiated into the most sacred Mysteries, the second, that we train the will for virtue." Nicholas Cabasilas, *The Life in Christ*, trans. Carmino J. deCatanaro (Crestwood, NY: St Vladimir's Seminary Press, 1974), 110 (PG 150:577-580, misattributed to Nilus, his uncle). As should become apparent from what is said below, the act of martyrdom, as kenotic self-offering, is a special combination of both of these. In so far as it is an act of the will first, but also insofar as it pours the martyr into the eucharistic cup of the suffering and self-sacrificial love of the Lord. It is also for this reason that the martyrs who were not given the chance to be baptised by water were understood to have been baptised by their own blood.

8 Here we find a precise reversal of Polycarp's name: καρπὸν πολύν.

9 In conjunction with Christ's explanation that "The seed is the word (*logos*) of God" (Lk 8:11), one may see parallels here with St Justin Martyr's "seminal

earth and die in order to bear fruit, for “unless a grain of wheat falls into the earth and dies, it remains alone; but if it dies, it bears much fruit (πολὸν καρπὸν)” (Jn 12:24).¹⁰ Because of the centrality of this concept in the teaching of Jesus, floral symbols would eventually come to occupy a preeminent place in communal worship and the life of the Church.

Earlier, serving as somewhat of a backdrop to all this, the sacrifices of ancient Israel were either consumed by the priests and those who had offered them, or else wholly offered up to God through burning.¹¹ These

logos” (λόγος σπερματικός) (PG 6:614-615). Borrowed and developed from the Stoic philosophy of his day, in its subsequent Patristic iteration, Christ the true Logos is as if implanted within the human race in the world. And in receiving the divine seeds (*logoi*) of Christ, who Himself grows up within the hearts of men, some will eventually come to bear fruit themselves and, by dying and being buried in the earth (Jn 12:24), plant the fruitful seed of the word again in the world.

- 10 In this passage again we find the root of Polycarp’s name (πολὸν καρπὸν), which would likely not be overlooked by the Greek speaking Christians of the period. Relative to this, Schoedel provides a very brief discussion of the history and use of the name Polycarp, which he believes likely to be original to the holy martyr. See Schoedel, *Polycarp, Martyrdom of Polycarp, Fragments of Papias*, 7 (subtext).
- 11 While there is some variation in how the types of sacrifices in the Levitical system are conceptually divided today, broadly speaking they were: 1) the sin offering, 2) the guilt offering, 3) the whole-burnt offering, 4) the present or gift, and 5) the peace offering. See Colin Brown, ‘Sacrifice,’ in *The New International Dictionary of New Testament Theology*, vol. 3, ed. Colin Brown (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 1975), 418-438. Their meanings and purposes were likewise varied. Of particular interest in the context of the martyrdom of St Polycarp is the whole-burnt offering or ‘ōlâh [וִּלְחָן], which the LXX translates from the Hebrew with the Greek *holokaustos* (ὁλόκαυστος), meaning ‘entirely consumed by fire’ or ‘wholly burnt.’ Even though there exists no etymological relationship, Colin Brown observes a link in the LXX with the Greek ‘ὁλόκαυστος’ and the phonetically similar offering of fruit or food ‘καρπός’: “The ‘ōlâh, is commonly translated ‘whole burnt offering.’ It is related to the vb ‘âlah, go up, hiph. cause to ascend, i.e. in the sacrificial fire. For this the LXX has *holokautōma* [ὁλοκαύτωμα] and *holokautōsis* [ὁλοκαύτωσις], ‘holocaust,’ and also *holokarpōma* [ὁλοκάρπωμα] and *holokarpōsis* [ὁλοκάρπωσις], ‘whole food offering,’ and *karpōma* [κάρπωμα] and *karpōsis* [κάρπωσις], ‘food offering.’” Colin Brown, ‘Sacrifice,’ 421. It has similarly been argued that in the ancient understanding the whole-burnt offering was meant to signify that the offering

latter were designated ‘whole-burnt offerings’ (Lev 1:9). To offer such a whole-burnt offering was to offer something entirely to God, so that nothing of the offering remained upon the earth to be eaten by those who offered the sacrifice or the priests who officiated. In this sense the act of offering a whole-burnt sacrifice embodied the idea that God had accepted and totally consumed the life or food which had been offered. By no accident the smoke of the offering symbolically ascended to heaven, the dwelling-place of God, which in both ancient Greek and Hebrew was the same word as that of the sky.¹² Thus, when the smoke of the burnt offering ascended to the sky, it figuratively ascended to the throne of God in heaven. As if highlighting the implicit ambiguity between life and food, these burnt sacrifices encompassed at different times animal and whole-grain offerings, as well as the bread of the presence (Judg 6:19-21). Similar parallels are found in later martyrdom accounts and hagiographies as well.

Symbolic Parallels in Other Ancient Martyrdom Accounts

While many of the symbolic elements discussed above appear in *The Martyrdom of Polycarp*, they are also present in other early martyrdom

had been ‘eaten’ by the god to which it had been offered. A parallel connection between the aroma of the cooked offering meal and the pleasing aroma that ascends to the father may be seen in Jacob’s “fragrant” offering of a savory meal to his father Isaac (Gen 27:4, 9-10, 27). Notably, it is by means of this offering that Jacob secures the blessing and inheritance from his father as the chosen son. Brown again writes: “The view that sacrifice is intended to provide food for the god is argued by W. Eichrodt, *Theology of the Old Testament*, I, 1961, 141 f.; E. Westermarck, *The Origin and Development of Moral Ideas*, 11, 1908, 611; R. H. Pfeiffer, *Religion in the Old Testament*, 1961, 35. Some support for taking this view in the OT has been found in certain idioms, such as ‘my table’ (Ezek 44:16), ‘the food of his God’ (Lev 21:22, cf. v. 17), ‘my food . . . my pleasing odour’ (Num 28:2).” He notes that the “furniture of the sacred tent and later of the temple (the table for the bread of the presence, the candelabrum, and the incense altar) have been seen as the means for providing Yahweh with the necessary means of partaking of the food offered.” Colin Brown, ‘Sacrifice,’ 424 (4.a).

- 12 The Greek *ouranós* (οὐρανός) and the Hebrew *šamayim* (שָׁמַיִם) are both used interchangeably for sky and heavens, referring more broadly throughout the scriptures to the upper chambers or the heights above.

accounts. One of the most obvious cases may be observed in *The Martyrdom of Ignatius*.¹³ In this regard, the connection between the two martyred saints and the symbolic nature of their deaths is reinforced by the fact that the two were personally acquainted and communicated in letters.¹⁴

In his *Epistle to the Romans*, St Ignatius' well-known statement likening himself to bread establishes not only the relationship between fruit and the Eucharist, but also the symbolic element of how the suffering of the righteous is refined through martyrdom: "Allow me to be food for beasts, through whom it is possible to reach God. I am God's wheat, and I am ground by the teeth of beasts, that I may be found pure bread of Christ."¹⁵ A similar concept is reinforced in the same epistle when St Ignatius again expresses his desire to the Roman community: "Grant me nothing more than to be poured out as an offering to God, while an altar is still ready..."¹⁶ Much like the imagery of bread, the pouring out of one's life as a libation cup evokes directly the imagery of fruitfulness and the vine. In this statement of kenotic self-abnegation echoes of St Paul's letter to the Philippians can be heard, according to

13 *Martyrium Ignatii*, PG 5:1894, 981C. See also 'The Martyrdom of Ignatius,' in *Ante-Nicene Fathers: The Writings of the Fathers down to A.D. 325*, ed. Alexander Roberts and James Donaldson (Peabody, MA: Hendrikson, 1995), vol. 1. Extensive discussion has already been made regarding the martyrdom of St Ignatius and his use of eucharistic imagery together with the concept of sacrifice. See Andrew McGowen, 'To Die for God: Sacrifice, Eucharist, and Martyrdom in Ignatius of Antioch,' in *Death and Rebirth in Late Antiquity*, ed. Lee M. Jefferson (Lanham: Rowman and Littlefield, 2022), 267-286; Peter-Ben Smit, 'On Being Consumed: The Martyred Body as a Site of Divine-Human Encounter in the Letters of Ignatius of Antioch,' *Religions* 11 (2020): 637.

14 Cf. 'Ignatius to Polycarp' in *The Apostolic Fathers*, 116-121 (PG 5:718-725).

15 St Ignatius of Antioch, 'Ignatius to the Romans', 4.1, in *The Apostolic Fathers*, 99 (PG 5:689).

16 St Ignatius of Antioch, 'Ignatius to the Romans', 2.2 (PG 5:687). Consider here again what has been said regarding the concept of sacrifice as *kenosis*, the pouring out of the self in love and in imitation of Christ. In the same passage, the saint also goes on to instruct the Christians in Rome to form a choir in singing a hymn to God for him in the act of his libation, thus integrating into the narrative the theme of a eucharistic hymn of thanksgiving (Mt 26:30).

which the Apostle says: “Even if I am to be poured as a libation upon the sacrificial offering of your faith, I am glad and rejoice with you all” (Phil 2:17).

By depicting himself as wheat, St Ignatius may have in mind the wheat passage in John 12:24. However, it should also be observed that Ignatius’ description establishes a link between the raw fruit of wheat and the product of its refinement, bread. The fruitful libation cup and the (wheat) bread of Christ, therefore, merge to form an obvious eucharistic allusion: “For I tell you that from now on I shall not drink of *the fruit of the vine* until the kingdom of God comes. And he took *bread*, and when he had given thanks he broke it and gave it to them, saying, “This is my body which is given for you. Do this in remembrance of me” (Lk 22:18-20). In this martyric context, the eucharistic bread is lifted up both as an offering and a representation of the perfection of the Christian life; that is, as an offering of selfless love poured out for the life and salvation of the world.¹⁷ And in this capacity, it is offered both as a fragrant sacrifice to God as well as an offering to be consumed. Such an offering not only produces fruit, but brings about eternal life. Hence again Ignatius’ statement: “Allow me to be food for beasts, through whom it is possible to reach God” (*Ign. Rom.*, 4.1).

It is also not coincidental that these themes—taken directly from the Gospel according to John—are shared in the writings and martyric

17 While somewhat later in origin, the words from the prayer of the consecration in the anaphora of St John Chrysostom are apropos (PG 63:791): “Who when He had come and had fulfilled all the dispensation for us, in the night in which He was given up—or rather, gave Himself up for the life of the world—took bread in His holy, pure, and blameless hands; and when He had given thanks and blessed it, and hallowed it, and broken it, He gave it to His holy disciples and apostles saying: ‘Take! Eat! This is My Body which is broken for you, for the remission of sins!’ [Choir:] Amen. [As the priest says the above words, the deacon points to the diskos with his orarion, and the priest prays...] And likewise, after supper, He took the cup, saying: ‘Drink of it, all of you! This is My Blood of the New Testament, which is shed for you and for many, for the remission of sins!’” ‘The Divine Liturgy of St John Chrysostom,’ in *The Service Books of the Orthodox Church* (South Canaan, PA: St Tikhon’s Seminary Press, 2010), 67-68.

depictions of both Sts Ignatius and Polycarp, as tradition holds that both were direct disciples of St John the Evangelist.¹⁸

Another early martyr, St Lawrence (225–258), is said to have been grilled alive by an enraged Roman prefect. Towards the end of the ‘cooking’ of his flesh, legend says that he remarked to his torturers: “I’m well done on this side. Turn me over!”¹⁹ Another very similar account is given of three martyrs—Macedonius, Theodulus, and Tatian—in Socrates’ *Church History*, according to which:

After subjecting them to all possible tortures [the governor Amachius] at last laid them on gridirons under which a fire was placed, and thus slew them. But even in this last extremity they gave the most heroic proofs of fortitude, addressing the ruthless

18 There are many literary and symbolic parallels between the epistles of Ignatius and John’s Gospel. For instance, St Ignatius’ use of the phrase “the prince of this world” (‘Ignatius to the Romans,’ 7, PG 5:693; Jn 14:30); also the larger theme of death and martyrdom as departure from this world (‘Ignatius to the Romans,’ 6-7, PG 5:691-693; Jn 13:1, 16:28). For a fairly detailed argument and analysis of selected passages, see Jerry L. Hayes. ‘Ignatius of Antioch and the Gospel of John: The Affinity in Thought and Expression.’ *Bishop’s Epistle* (blog), May 31, 2018. <https://bishopjerryhayes.blogspot.com/2018/05/ignatius-of-antioch-and-gospel-of-john.html> (though his scope is somewhat narrow); likewise Charles Hill follows Lightfoot and Inge in seeing parallels in Ignatius’ use of “door / θύρα” (‘Ignatius to the Philadelphians,’ 9, PG 5:703; Jn 10:7, 9, 14:6), noting another stronger parallel in the line “For [the Spirit] knows from where it came and where it is going...” (‘Ignatius to the Philadelphians,’ 7, PG 5:701; Jn 3:8, 8:14); Charles E. Hill, ‘Ignatius, the ‘Gospel,’ and the Gospels,’ in *Trajectories through the New Testament and the Apostolic Fathers*, ed. A. Gregory and C. Tucket (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2005), 267-85, footnotes 36 & 39; For the historical or legendary association of St Polycarp with St John the Evangelist, see Irenaeus, *Against Heresies*, 3, 3, 4 (PG 7:848-849); Tertullian, *Prescription Against Heretics*, 32, cf. *De Præscriptione Hæreticorum* in Migne, *Patrologia Latina* (= PL), vol. 2, col. 44; Jerome, *Illustrious Men (De Viris Illustribus)*, 17 (PL 23:858).

19 Some have raised doubts as to the reliability of Lawrence being martyred by being grilled alive and have instead put forth the theory that it was an early grammatical error in the account of his martyrdom. Regardless of its historicity, the hagiographical legend reinforces the idea of St Lawrence’s body being offered up as ‘food.’ See, for example, Lawrence B. Porter, ‘St Lawrence’s Death on a Grill: Fact or Fiction?’, *Logos* 20.4 (2020): 89-111.

governor thus: “If you wish to eat broiled flesh, Amachius, turn us on the other side also, lest we should appear but half cooked to your taste.” Thus these martyrs ended their life.²⁰

As all of these accounts show, there was a clear association in the mind of early Christians between the body of the martyr, offered as food or bread, and the earlier biblical understanding of a consumed sacrifice. Even if, in some cases, such an association was meant as a mockery of the pagan authorities and their attacks on the Church.

Fruitful Polycarp

Though itself among the earliest, *The Martyrdom of Polycarp* contains many parallel symbolic themes with other early Christian martyrdom accounts as well as numerous typological parallels with the Passion narratives in the Gospels. Polycarp, like Christ, is betrayed by those close to him, arrested by a man named Herod, carried into town on an ass, and pierced in the side after being killed, to mention only a few of the

20 Here is the passage in full: “Amachius governor of Phrygia ordered that the temple at Merum, a city of that province, should be opened, and cleared of the filth which had accumulated there by lapse of time: also that the statues it contained should be polished fresh. This in being put into operation grieved the Christians very much. Now a certain Macedonius and Theodulus and Tatian, unable to endure the indignity thus put upon their religion, and impelled by a fervent zeal for virtue, rushed by night into the temple, and broke the images in pieces. The governor, infuriated at what had been done, would have put to death many in that city who were altogether innocent, when the authors of the deed voluntarily surrendered themselves, choosing rather to die themselves in defence of the truth, than to see others put to death in their stead. The governor seized and ordered them to expiate the crime they had committed by sacrificing: on their refusal to do this, their judge menaced them with tortures; but they despising his threats, being endowed with great courage, declared their readiness to undergo any sufferings, rather than pollute themselves by sacrificing. After subjecting them to all possible tortures he at last laid them on gridirons under which a fire was placed, and thus slew them. But even in this last extremity they gave the most heroic proofs of fortitude, addressing the ruthless governor thus: ‘If you wish to eat broiled flesh, Amachius, turn us on the other side also, lest we should appear but half cooked to your taste.’ Thus these martyrs ended their life.” Socrates, *Church History*, Book 3, Chapter 15 (PL 67:190B), New Advent: <https://www.newadvent.org/fathers/26013.htm>.

typological similarities.²¹ No less prominent in the account are literary-symbolic depictions of fruit and food, which form a literary motif on their own.

The primary reason to view the martyrdom through the framework of floral symbolism, however, is that the name ‘Polycarp’ (Πολύκαρπος) literally means ‘very fruitful’ or ‘many fruited.’ The significance of a person’s name—and its connection to that person’s deep spiritual identity or destiny—is one of the more ancient and enduring concepts. In this way, Adam was invited by God to name the animals in one of the first liturgical acts of creation and synergy between God and man (Gen 2:19-20). Because Adam’s name itself means ‘man,’ defining the animals was itself an act of self-actualisation for him.²² For it was both Adam and man’s divinely appointed destiny to “have dominion over the fish of the sea and over the birds of the air and over every living thing that moves upon the earth” (Gen 1:28). Likewise, Abraham—formerly called

21 In her study of the martyrdom of Polycarp, Stephanie Cobb, comparing the martyrdom to both the passion of Christ as well as to that of Socrates, makes note of all the ways in which Polycarp acts in *imitatio* of Christ: “... like Jesus, Polycarp waits to be handed over (1.2); he is not far from the city when he is arrested (5.1); he prophesies his death (5.2; 12.3); he is betrayed by someone close to him (6.2); a man named Herod plays a part in his death (6.2); he is sought as a robber (7.1); he is apprehended at night (7.1-2); he chooses not to flee, preferring instead that God’s ‘will be done’ (7.1); he is led into the city on an ass (8.1); a Roman ruler is reluctant to sentence him to death (9.3-11.2); the crowd calls for his death (3.2; 12.2-13.1); the Jews are particularly instrumental in his death (13.1); he is stabbed (16.1); the Jews raise concerns about the Christians receiving his body (17.2); and he dies on a Sabbath, perhaps at Passover (21).” Stephanie Cobb, ‘Polycarp’s Cup: *Imitatio* in the Martyrdom of Polycarp,’ *Journal of Religious History* 38.2 (2014): 224-240, here 224.

22 Though not the focus here, much can be said in this respect to the nature of naming or defining through the spoken word. It is by and through the ‘word of the Lord’ that creation is brought into being from the beginning (Gen 1:3, 5, 6; Jn 1:1-2, Heb 1:3). Likewise, to be given a name is the locus of great ontological significance which comes to assert itself on the person or named object. A child without a name lacks, in some fundamental sense, an identity until it is given a name; this is why, in the Orthodox Church, a child is not given a name until the moment of baptism, emphasising in this way that a person’s true identity ultimately rests in Christ.

Abram—received his name and became ‘the father of many’ through faith in God’s promise realised in the birth of his true son, Isaac (Gen 17:5).²³ Through his martyrdom Polycarp similarly attains to self-actualisation, as it is primarily by means of his suffering and witness that he becomes ‘fruitful.’

The account of his martyrdom depicts this in a number of overlapping ways, many of which come to be subtly connected both to the sacrifice of the martyrs and the Eucharist. In one key passage which describes the nature of his martyrdom, the narrator explains that his executioners intended to nail him to the pyre but instead tied him, as the noble Polycarp reassured them that he would not depart from the flames:

And they did not nail him, but they tied him, and having put his hands behind him and having been bound, just like a choice ram from a great flock for a sacrifice, a whole-burnt offering, made ready and acceptable to God” (MartPol 14.1).²⁴

The saint is therefore depicted, first of all, as both a living sacrifice and simultaneously as fruit hung upon, but not nailed to, the stake. In fact the martyrdom emphasises in several places that St Polycarp must die—much like a “choice ram,” selected and “bound up” for sacrifice—by being “burned alive,” as this was revealed to him in a vision by God three days before his martyrdom (MartPol 5.2, 11.1-2, 12.3).

One possible way of reading the detail of Polycarp being tied to the wooden stake rather than being nailed to it is to contextualise it within

23 The name *Abram* (אַבְרָם) means “blessed father,” while the name *Abraham* (אַבְרָהָם)—which he is given by the Angel of the Lord upon the coming of the promised son—means “father of many.”

24 All passages from ‘The Martyrdom of Polycarp’ (henceforth simply ‘MartPol’) are taken from the English translation of Brannan cited above: ‘The Martyrdom of Saint Polycarp Bishop of Smyrna,’ in *The Apostolic Fathers*, 262-276. Lightfoot’s translation is also recommended: ‘The Letter to the Smyrnaeans,’ in *The Apostolic Fathers*, trans. J. B. Lightfoot (Cambridge, OH: Christian Publishing House, 2020), 82-92. All in-text citations follow the traditional section and line numbering.

the ancient concept and practice of grafting. In his letter to the Romans, St Paul uses this imagery in his letter to the Romans as a symbolic allegory for the inclusion of Gentile Christians into the people of God. “But if some of the branches were broken off, and you, a wild olive shoot, were grafted in their place to share the richness of the olive tree, do not boast over the branches. If you do boast, remember it is not you that support the root, but the root that supports you” (Rom 11:17-18).²⁵ Such an association is bolstered by the likelihood that Polycarp was one of the earliest Gentile converts to Christianity, as well as, again, in the implication of the name ‘Polycarp,’ which designates him as fruitful. By being grafted onto the sacrificial pyre, Polycarp is therefore symbolically and mystically grafted onto the vine of Christ (Jn 15:1-8), the same vine who is himself a branch springing forth from the stump of Jesse (Isa 11:1).²⁶

Immediately after the account of him being tied to the pyre to be burned, his final prayer reads as a kind of eucharistic anaphora, within which the holy man supplicates God with the following words:

I bless you because you have considered me worthy of this day and hour, that I might receive a share among the number of the martyrs in the cup of your Christ, to the resurrection of life eternal ... (MartPol 14.2)

The “cup” in the anaphora prayer of St Polycarp is linked symbolically

- 25 Before being judged and ascending the stake to be burned, a supernatural voice resounded in the stadium admonishing him with the words: “Be strong, Polycarp, and play the man” (9:1). Thus in order to be grafted onto the pyre, and symbolically into the people of God, it is implied that he must have faith and endurance. The passage of St Paul to the Romans carries the same implication: “You will say, ‘Branches were broken off so that I might be grafted in.’ That is true. They were broken off because of their unbelief, but you stand fast only through faith. So do not become proud, but stand in awe” (Rom 11:19-20).
- 26 This passage from the book of Isaiah probably has in mind the dissolution of the house of David which had been “cut off” and is therefore anticipating directly a future restoration of the Davidic line and kingdom with the coming of the Messiah. See R. Coggins, ‘Isaiah,’ in *The Oxford Bible Commentary*, ed. John Barton and John Muddiman (New York: Oxford University Press, 2001), 448.

with the passionate suffering of the mystical members of the body of Christ, and the martyr himself is as if juiced or threshed through suffering and poured as wine offering into the eucharistic cup. By means of the self-consecrating prayer of Polycarp, then, the eucharistic communion of all is blurred to include the bodily suffering of the martyrs, which come to be united mystically with the suffering of Christ and offered for the life of the world.

The words of this prayer, as in many early Christian martyric depictions, effectively bring together several seemingly disparate symbolic themes discussed in various passages of Holy Scripture. For example: “This cup which is poured out for you is the new covenant in my blood” (Lk 22:20). In another similar passage, Christ addresses the desire of James and John to sit at his right and left hand in places of honour: “You do not know what you are asking. Are you able to drink the cup that I am to drink?” (Mt 20:22). And finally the confession of St Paul, that he completes in his own flesh the suffering of Christ: “Now I rejoice in my sufferings for your sake, and in my flesh I complete what is lacking in Christ’s afflictions for the sake of his body, that is, the Church” (Col 1:24; cf 1 Pet 4:1).

The trope of martyric suffering as “grafting” onto Christ is echoed within the hymnography of the Church in the Vespers service for the feast of St Polycarp:

When the True Vine had been lifted up * hanging on the wood of the Cross, then He put thee forth as a branch * which, on bringing forth much fruit, was hewn down with the scythe * of a ven’rable martyrdom * and fully was trod out * in the vat and wine-press of most painful punishments; * having mixed the wine-bowl of gladness * from these things in faith, O wise Father, * we all glorify thy sacred contests now.²⁷

27 *The February Menaion*, trans. Holy Transfiguration Monastery (Boston, MA: Holy Transfiguration Monastery, 2005), 130. The hymn cited above is a translation of the second *sticheron* at Vespers: Ὅτε ἐπὶ ξύλου τοῦ Σταυροῦ, ἡ ἀληθινὴ κρεμασθεῖσα, ὑψώθη ἄμπελος, τότε σὲ κατάκαρπον, κλήμα ἐξέτεινε,

As can be seen, this hymn unites together the themes of Polycarp as a grafted branch upon the tree of the Cross, together with his being poured out into the eucharistic cup of the suffering of Christ. It is, therefore, by the very act of being offered up as fruit on the vine of the pyre that Polycarp achieves grafting and fruitfulness. His suffering on the pyre and his blood being poured out into the “wine-bowl of gladness” are, in this context, implicit symbolic representations of his being threshed, treaded, or juiced as a cluster of grapes into the eucharistic cup of the Lord.

After having thus offered himself to God, the *Martyrdom* observes:

Finally, then, the lawless one, seeing his body could not be consumed by the fire, ordered an executioner to go up and stab him with a dagger. And having done this, a dove came out, and a large amount of blood, so that it quenched the fire ... (MartPol 16.1)

It is possible here to see a parallel first in the piercing of the side of Christ with the spear (Jn 19:34), and second an implication according to which the blood of Christ—and also the martyr—quenches the raging fires of hell.²⁸ Polycarp’s fruitfulness therefore becomes manifest as a libation poured out into the cup of suffering, a cup associated directly with Christ, and offered in the case of the martyrs also, by means of their own passionate suffering—fulfilling the biblical admonition of St Paul “...to present your bodies as a living sacrifice, holy and acceptable to God, which is your spiritual worship” (Rom 12:1).

τῆ δρεπάνῃ τεμνόμενον, σεπτοῦ μαρτυρίου, καὶ τοῖς τῶν κολάσεων, ληνοῖς πατούμενον, οὐπερ εὐφροσύνης κρατῆρα, πίστει συγκεράσαντες, Πάτερ, τοὺς σεπτοὺς ἀγῶνάς σου δοξάζομεν. For the original Greek text of the hymns, see Ἁγ. Ἱερομάρτυρος Πολυκάρπου ἀρχιεπισκόπου Σμύρνης (κγ’), in Μηναιὸν τοῦ Φεβρουαρίου, ed. Ἀποστολικὴ Διακονία τῆς Ἐκκλησίας τῆς Ἑλλάδος, Athens (1972).

28 The saint alludes to this in one place, defiantly telling the proconsul: “You threaten with fire that burns for a while, and after a little time is extinguished. For you are ignorant of the fire of the coming judgement and eternal punishment” (MartPol. 11.2). Moreover, the “dove” can be seen as a symbol of the Holy Spirit, and that of the martyr—itself a Eucharistic image, given the invocation of the Holy Spirit in the *epiclesis* during the liturgical anaphora.

Martyred Polycarp as Bread and Whole-Burnt Offering

In addition to the cup, associated with the fruit of the vine and suffering, Polycarp's martyrdom also depicts his body as bread, baked within the fire of the pyre:

For the fire, taking on the form of a vaulted room, like the sail of a ship filled by wind, completely surrounded the body of the martyr. And the body was in the middle, not like flesh burning, but like bread baking, or like gold and silver being refined in a furnace. For we perceived also an intense fragrance like the scent of incense or some other precious spice. (MartPol, 15.2)

The narrator's reference to bread and frankincense may be an allusion to the use of those offerings in the Tabernacle and the Temple (cf. Ex 30:34-38), where the table for the bread of the presence was opposite that of the altar of incense and the menorah. The perfume which was offered to the Lord in this manner was required not to be used for any earthly or profane purpose. Moreover, the incense used in the Temple symbolised both the prayer of God's people ascending to the throne of God in heaven (Ps 141:2; Rev 8:4), and also the Spirit of the Lord resting upon the people. Whether deliberate or unintended, the body of holy Polycarp is presented in the martyrdom in precisely this way as baked bread and aromatic frankincense, a holy oblation to God; and just as with the martyrdom of St Ignatius, here the depiction of the martyr's body as bread bears strong association with the bread of the Eucharist, the holy body of Christ.

According to the narrator of the text, after the martyrdom of St Polycarp is complete, the Roman authorities are provoked by some Jews to entirely dispose of his body by burning. This is done so that his followers will not steal him away, as was said to have been done by Christians with the body of Jesus (cf. Mt 28:11-15):

Therefore the centurion, seeing the dispute raised by the Jews, having placed [the martyr's body] in the middle, as is their

custom, he burned it. And so we finally took away his bones,
more precious than costly stones and honored more than gold.
We deposited them in a fitting place. (MartPol 18.1-2)

In this capacity, the burning of the body of St Polycarp presents a narrative depiction of the martyr as “a whole-burnt offering, made ready and acceptable to God” (MartPol 14.1). This imagery is reinforced in the martyrdom account, which specifies that Polycarp’s disciples not only sought to touch his feet while he was alive (MartPol 13.2), but that they desired earnestly to share in his holy flesh after his martyrdom. For, the narrator observes, the body of the martyr was burned despite the fact that “many [of us] desired to do this [i.e., to take away his body] and to have a share (κοινωνῆσαι, lit. “to commune”)²⁹ in his holy flesh” (MartPol 17.1). Their desire to partake and commune with the holy martyr through contact with his holy flesh was therefore specifically prevented by the fact that his body was entirely consumed by fire.

By being entirely consumed with nothing remaining, the martyr is effectively portrayed, implicitly at least, as a whole-burnt offering to God. While St Polycarp may be presented in symbolic terms as fruit, bread, and food which many desire to partake of and share, no one is able to eat from those offerings as they are accepted and consumed entirely by God, with the added symbolic implication that the martyr is now present in the cup of Christ (MartPol 14.2).

Symbolic Depictions in Hymnography

What has been said above is, perhaps unsurprisingly, reflected in the hymnography of the Orthodox Church, which is equally replete with eucharistic symbolism—particularly within the service composed in honour of “the Holy Hieromartyr Polycarp, Bishop of Smyrna” contained in the Greek recension of the *Menaion* published by the Church of Greece.³⁰

29 Though the word ‘κοινωνῆσαι’ means ‘to commune’ it also means ‘to come into contact.’ Lightfoot chose to translate it more literally as “to touch,” whereas Brannan opted for the more moderate “to share.”

30 For the full Greek service: Ἁγ. Ἱερομάρτυρος Πολυκάρπου αρχιεπισκόπου

Most striking within the hymnographical corpus is a hymn from the Vespers mentioned above, which weaves together the central themes of Polycarp as a grafted branch upon the tree of the Cross and that of the martyr being poured out (cf. Phil 2:17) into the eucharistic cup as a kenotic libation.³¹ For it is in this way that Polycarp unites his own sufferings to those of Christ the Master. Polycarp is described as a “branch ... of the True Vine ... hewn down with the scythe of a venerable martyrdom ... fully trod out in the vat and wine-press of most painful punishments; having mixed the wine-bowl of gladness from these things in faith.”³² Moreover, he is called out as a “vine-branch” (κλήμα) of that Vine, preeminently “fruitful” (κατάκαρπον), “pruned” (τεμνόμενον) as it were by his martyrdom.

In another *sticheron*, Polycarp is called the “holy fruit” of the Virgin and “a most fruitful ear of wheat” (πολύκαρπον στάχυν).³³ Such descriptions establish a clear connection to the blood of his martyrdom and his priestly ministry (αἵματι καὶ ἱερωσύνης), as well as to the meaning of his name. And again in the original Greek the aforementioned hymn calls him ζωαρχικώτατος σπόρος³⁴ (lit., a “most life-originating seed,” of which phrase the adjective ζωαρχικός appears occasionally in other services of the Church).³⁵

Σμύρνης (κγ’), in Μηναιὸν τοῦ Φεβρουαρίου, cited above; and in English, *Menaion*, 129-135.

31 Hymn of the second *sticheron*: “When the True Vine had been lifted up * hanging on the wood of the Cross, then He put thee forth as a branch * which, on bringing forth much fruit, was hewn down with the scythe * of a ven’rable martyrdom * and fully was trod out * in the vat and wine-press of most painful punishments; * having mixed the wine-bowl of gladness * from these things in faith, O wise Father, * we all glorify thy sacred contests now.” *Menaion*, 130.

32 *Menaion*, 130.

33 “When the blameless Virgin’s holy Fruit * and the Seed whence all of life springeth had fallen into the earth, then He shot thee forth as a most fruitful ear of wheat, who didst feed with the words and deeds * of godly religion * all His faithful flock, while also sanctifying them * with the godly blood of thy contest, * cleansing them as well with the sweet myrrh * of thy priestly ministry, a Polycarp.” *Menaion*, 129.

34 *Menaion*, 130.

35 With or without the superlative suffix, the word ζωαρχικός is attributed to the

In the Vespereal *Doxastikon*, Polycarp is said to have “cultivated” his soul with inspired sayings in order to “treasure up the blessed fruit of grace.” The trope of the banquet is seen again in the third *sticheron* of the *Aposticha*, as “all the worshippers of God the Holy Trinity” are said to “feast on [his] virtues.”³⁶ This last reference in particular may be linked with the biblical teaching of Christ regarding false teachers and prophets expressed in Matthew: “You will know them by their fruits. Are grapes gathered from thorns, or figs from thistles?” (Mt 7:16, cf. 15-20).

The *Doxastikon* at the *Aposticha* is remarkable in particular, in that it directly connects the grace of sanctity and martyric struggle, not only with the fruit of the vine in general, but also the “wine of compunction,” itself a reference to Psalm 60. This latter is generally taken as a reference to humility in the face of great trials, but also extended to the trope of a banquet or sacrificial meal:³⁷

Since thou didst truly cultivate [γεωργήσας] the cluster of grace [χάριτος βότρυον] in thy soul, O wise Father, thou madest the doctrines of faith to gush forth as the wine of compunction [ὡς οἶνον ἐξέβλυσας], making glad the minds of the faithful and proving to be a boundless sea of miracles. Wherefore, when thou wast perfected by fire [πυρὶ τελειούμενος], thou becamest the comeliness of Martyrs and a partaker of the everlasting divine light, O blessed Polycarp; intercede with Christ God, the Saviour of our souls, Who was inexpressibly incarnate, that we also may partake of the light.³⁸

The third ode of the Matins canon composed by Theophanes begins by

Theotokos or the saints in the liturgical hymnography (e.g., the *Menaion* service for St Onesiphorus appointed for November 9). It appears in the Patristic corpus as well, in connection with the Theotokos (cf. John of Scythopolis, *Scholion on the Divine Names* 236.8, misattributed to Maximus the Confessor in PG 4:236C, 1-5).

36 *Menaion*, 130.

37 This is especially true, since “the bread of sorrow” (cf. Ps 127:2) is often connected to the image of this wine.

38 *Menaion*, 131. For the Greek, this hymn can be found in the ἀκολουθία contained in the February Μηνναῖον, viz. the *Doxastikon* at the *Aposticha* from Vespers.

calling Polycarp “a fruitful olive tree”³⁹; immediately thereafter, the first sessional hymn exhibits eucharistic and sacrificial references, saying that Polycarp “cultivate[d] the sweet cluster of grace, gush[ing] forth ... wine of the doctrine of saving faith [τὸν τῆς χάριτος βότρυν ... γεωργήσας ... ὡς οἶνον ἐξέβλυσας...],”⁴⁰ whereas Ode Four calls him both a “plant... [of] much fruit” as well as “a perfect whole-burnt offering and a pure sacrifice.”⁴¹ After the sixth ode, the *Oikos* is at once eucharistic and sacrificial, since Polycarp is said to “[offer] the souls of them that believed as ripe fruit unto him in Whom we have been baptised.”⁴² These dual themes of fruit and sacrifice, respectively, are echoed by Ode Seven, which depicts Polycarp as one who “offer[s] Christ once-fruitless souls, made fruitful by the cultivation of the Spirit”⁴³—as well as by the verses at the *Synaxarion*, which call him a “whole-burnt offering, yielding much fruit [ὠλοκαυτώθη ... καρπὸν πολλὸν δοῦς] from out of the fire most strangely.”⁴⁴ In Ode Eight, this same idea is developed further, where the holy martyr is called in the first *Troparion* a “rational oblation” (λογικὸν ἱερεῖον), who is “slaughtered like an auspicious ram for the sake of Christ” (Ode 8, *Troparion* 4). Here the comparison of the martyr to an “auspicious ram” in the Church hymnography echoes a similar comparison in the narrative account (MartPol 14.1).

Following this imagery, the second hymn at the *Aposticha* of the Praises calls on the saint to “raise [up his] august and priestly hands, and now as of old, present [God] with the unbloody and very dread Sacrifice,” in which the martyr himself participates as a “sacrifice pleasing unto God.”⁴⁵ In all this the martyr comes to imitate Christ in the Eucharist as the one who is both the offeror and the one who is offered.

39 Cf. Ps 52:8, “ἐλαία ... κατάκαρπος.”

40 *Menaion*, 131.

41 ὀλοκαύτωμα τέλειον, καὶ καθαρὰ θυσία.

42 ψυχὰς πιστευόντων προσάγων τούτῳ ... ἐν ᾧ βεβαπτίσμεθα.

43 Ἀκάρπους τὸ πρίν, πολυκάρπους τῷ Χριστῷ ψυχὰς προσήνεγκας, γεωργία τῆ τοῦ Πνεύματος.

44 *Menaion*, 133.

45 *Menaion*, 135.

Conclusion

As has been shown, *The Martyrdom of Polycarp* provides us with a symbolic framework according to the early Christian conception of the martyr as food and the martyric act of offering as fruitfulness. By imitating St Polycarp, early Gentile martyrs could likewise mystically fulfill St Paul's symbolic depiction of being grafted onto the fruitful tree of the cross and the passionate suffering of Christ. In doing so, they became symbolically and sacramentally included in the eucharistic cup of the communion of the saints and the Church. Martyric literature of this kind, therefore, effectively presents a very early ecclesiology, according to which the eucharistic meal of Christ is mystically synonymous with the individual members of the Church—who are likewise to offer themselves up as bread, food, libation, and fruit. This act of self-offering is embodied particularly in the martyrs, who are offered up with Christ for the life and salvation of the world.

The martyrs of the early Church, therefore, fulfilled the Apostle's admonition in the Epistle to the Romans: "I appeal to you therefore, brethren, by the mercies of God, to present your bodies as a living sacrifice, holy and acceptable to God, which is your spiritual worship" (Rom 12:1). For by presenting their bodies as a living sacrifice, the martyrs effectively gave themselves up entirely to God as whole-burnt offerings, and were in return fully united to God in Christ. Consumed entirely by fire, grilled, or baked, they became imitators of Christ and gave themselves up in this manner as fragrant meal-offerings to God. St Polycarp himself, then, is reckoned among the first-fruits of the eternal and everlasting banquet feast of Christ the Bridegroom (cf. Mt 22:1-14; Rev 19:7-9).